

Iteration 3: Lentune Bug Reproduction Process Action Research

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1. Addressable findings from pervious study

In study 2 we addressed some items from the backlog ([TaskBackLog.xlsx](#)) while we are waiting for the outcome of study 2. We start to look into other items in the backlog can be addressed in this study based on the resource available and priorities of the Lentune development team. Following are the items selected to be addressed at this study:

- I1.1.1 Missing logs of end-user actions (e.g., URLs, timestamps, session replay)
- I1.1.2 Lack of system configuration tracking
- I1.2.3 Incomplete error logs without contextual information
- I1.3.1 Gaps in monitoring resource usage (e.g., CPU, RAM)
- I1.3.3 Lack of network traffic analysis during bugs

2. Action Points Planned for this Study Cycle

By evaluating (1) the gaps identified in the study 1, (2) resource available in Lentune and (3) priority of the work Lentune development, we decide to implement the following modifications to our intervention:

2.1 Close Information Gaps for Client-End Data:

- **2.1.1 End user interaction data:** To address the work item I1.1.1, we aim to expand Datadog for broader user action data collection in last iteration. However, due to inadequate support from the Datadog team, we will seek an alternative solution in this iteration.
- **2.1.2 Collect context data:** To address the work item I1.1.2, client-side context data helps developers understand bugs better and replicate the debugging environment similar to the customer's local setup.

2.2 Close Information Gaps for Back-End Data:

- **2.2.1 Collect context data:** To address the work item I1.2.3, we gather back-end context to help developers create an environment similar to production for bug reproduction.

2.3 Close Information Gaps for Infrastructure Data:

- **2.3.1 Resource usage data:** To address the work item I1.3.1, we monitor hosting environment status to assist developers in reproducing bugs related to resource usage.
- **2.3.2 Network traffic data:** To address the work item I1.3.3, we collect application network traffic data to aid developers in diagnostics and bug reproduction.

3 Implementation details

In this section, we discuss the actions taken to address the action points mentioned in Section 2.

3.1 Implement PostHog for user action data collection:

To address things discussed under item 2.1.1 above, we aimed to enhance our data collection by implementing DataDog in the last iteration, but the support team could not provide the necessary guidance for our business needs. As a result, we explored alternatives and found PostHog, which meets our user action data collection requirements and has a responsive support team. However, unlike DataDog, PostHog does not collect backend and infrastructure data. For Lentune, having a reliable partner with good support is more important than extra functionality without support. Therefore, we will integrate PostHog into our software and roll it out to all customers while continuing to use DataDog.

3.2 Collect context data for the bug report:

In this iteration, we aim to collect context data for the bug report raised.

For the front-end context data (discussed under item 2.1.2 above), we will use PostHog to collect information:

- Device type: what type of device users are using (e.g., tablet, mobile phone, or computer)
- OS version: what version of the operating system users' devices are running (e.g., Windows, Mac OS, Android, or iOS)
- Browser version: what version of the browser is used by users (e.g., Chrome, Edge, Firefox)
- Software version: the version of Lentune software users are using (front-end)

For the backend context data (discussed under item 2.2.1 above), we will start to collect:

- **Server name:** the name of the server that processed the request for the reported bug. The Lentune application is hosted on multiple instances to ensure performance, so it is important to understand if the error only happened on a specific instance of the application which may suggest an infrastructure related problem rather than a code problem.
- **Software version:** the version of the Lentune software that processed the request (backend).
- **Configuration environment:** the environment the application is configured for (e.g., Dev, Testing, Beta, Production)

3.3 Collect infrastructure data for the bug report:

In this iteration, we will also start to collect the infrastructure data related to the bug report raised. This includes (1) server resource usage monitoring (discussed under item 2.3.1 above) and (2) network traffic data analysis (discussed under item 2.3.2 above).

3.3.1 Server resource usage monitoring:

The server resource usage monitoring focuses on two categories: compute resources and database resources. The compute resources are mainly distributed between virtual machines (VM) and Azure app service plans. Both compute resources have basic monitoring functions provided by Azure, but due to the data being distributed, it is challenging for developers to query and diagnose the bugs reported. In this iteration, we merged the monitoring data of VMs and App service plans into one location and generated a dashboard for developers to visualize the monitoring data.

Similarly, the database has the same problem. Basic resource usage monitoring is available out-of-the-box from Azure SQL; however, the data for different databases is distributed. We merged all monitoring data into the same storage location and created a dashboard for developers to access the data when required. Additionally, we merged the compute resources and database resources into the same dashboard so developers can see all resource usage in one location, expediting the data query process further.

3.3.2 Network traffic data analysis:

Since Lentune is a web application where client-end apps connect to the back end using APIs, it is important for Lentune developers to understand network traffic when a bug is reported. In this iteration, we improved the implementation of Azure Application Insight (AI) to capture the network traffic of Lentune API. Based on previous experiments with AI, the cost is high for the Lentune team. Therefore, we are running a sampling of the network traffic collected at this study. We hope the data collected will help developers better understand the network traffic occurring during the periods when bugs happen.

4 Lessons learned

4.1 Access control must be considered when implementing a monitoring system.

We encountered an issue where support team members could not access monitoring data due to different access levels compared to developers. To resolve this, we moved the monitoring infrastructure to a separate environment with broader access, distinct from production. The takeaway is that monitoring infrastructure should be implemented outside of the production environment to maintain compliance and security settings.

4.2 Data visualisation is an important and challenging task.

In this study phase, we implemented extensive context data collection. We discovered that individual data points may not always contribute significantly to the bug diagnostic process. However, when these data points are integrated with other relevant metrics through visualisation, they become valuable pieces of information for bug reproduction. For instance, in a bug related to hosting resources, examining the average resource usage alone might not reveal any issues. Yet, by combining the data with the instance name of the hosting machine and visualising them in different series, we quickly identified that high resource usage occurs only on one specific hosting machine instance, rather than all of them. This insight allows developers to focus on the problematic machine and ultimately resolve the issue. With these lessons learned, we began migrating related data and creating dashboards based on the bug reports we handle.

4.3 Cost management is a task need continues monitoring.

During the study phase, we implemented PostHog to replace DataDog because it required less technical skill and better supported the Lentune team. However, after rolling out PostHog, the usage pricing increased significantly from the initial estimate. The Lentune team estimated \$5 per customer, but post-rollout, the cost rose to \$25 per customer due to increased usage and some preview modules becoming chargeable.

This made PostHog no longer cost-effective for Lentune, leading the development and product team to pause its use and revert changes. They are now considering other alternatives for client-end monitoring. The cost increase was discovered during the billing cycle by the Lentune account team. This highlighted the importance of having a real-time alert-based pricing monitoring system to minimize financial impact. Lentune will ensure this is a checkpoint for all future SaaS products it acquires.

4.4 New technology means new monitoring approaches are need.

New technologies often bring fresh challenges and requirements for monitoring and bug reproduction debugging. During the recent study study, we identified webhooks as a new area that required a monitoring process for the relevant bug reports. In our previous

study, a similar need was identified for the new AI-related functionalities. These findings underscore the necessity of integrating new monitoring approaches whenever new technologies or functionalities are introduced.

As a result, we learned that it is crucial for developers to consider the implementation of monitoring systems whenever they adopt new technologies or approaches within the codebase. This proactive step ensures that any potential issues can be promptly identified and addressed, maintaining the overall health and performance of the application.

5 Interviews with system users

This section presents feedback from three stakeholders involved in Lentune's bug reproduction process during Study 3:

- **Gareth** – Customer Support
- **Alex** – Junior Developer
- **Marc** – Senior Developer

Their insights focus on the impact of new monitoring tools, usability, system performance, and integration with workflows.

5.1 Experience with the Current Bug Reproduction Process

Alex noted that the newly added context and network traffic data significantly improved debugging, especially for backend API issues. However, due to Azure Application Insights' sampling strategy, some crucial data was occasionally missing. He also mentioned that not all users followed the bug report template properly, which led to missing key data. He had not yet used the resource usage monitoring.

Marc observed that while the bug reproduction process hadn't drastically changed from the previous cycle, the added context and network information were useful when handling customer-specific backend bugs. He echoed concerns about data sampling in Application Insights and mentioned he had not yet found a use case for the resource monitoring data. Marc also reiterated that PostHog lacked the usability of DataDog.

Gareth reported that the process had improved considerably, especially with the introduction of resource monitoring. He found the resource usage data particularly helpful for diagnosing performance issues and isolating problems to specific customer environments. While he hadn't yet used the network log, he praised the context data,

especially OS and browser information, for helping with frontend bug reproduction. However, he found PostHog less intuitive than DataDog.

Summary:

All interviewees noted improved bug reproducibility from new context and monitoring data. Resource usage monitoring was particularly helpful for Gareth, while data sampling and PostHog's usability posed common challenges. The bug report quality remains inconsistent across users.

5.2 System Usability

Alex described the system as generally usable but mentioned the learning curve associated with Azure's KQL querying for network traffic. He noted that a SQL-based querying option would be preferable.

Marc felt the system allowed him to get his work done but emphasized the inefficiency caused by scattered data across different monitoring platforms. He recommended unifying the monitoring data into a single dashboard for easier access.

Gareth shared that while he could effectively use API logs, his access to other data sources—particularly network traffic logs—was restricted. He found DataDog easier to navigate for user action tracking compared to PostHog.

Summary:

Usability is mixed: developers like Alex and Marc can manage but are slowed down by tool fragmentation and non-standard query languages, while Gareth is constrained by access limitations. A centralized and simplified querying system is broadly desired.

5.3 System Performance

Alex stated the system captured most of the necessary data, but highlighted that AI-related issues were still difficult to debug due to the lack of model input/output data. He mentioned that frontend exceptions were caught by DataDog, but coverage was not consistent across all users.

Marc said that the system provided sufficient data for most diagnostics but called out a new gap related to webhook debugging. As his recent work involves webhooks from external systems, he noted the absence of logs detailing how webhook data is processed and received, which limits his ability to trace issues end-to-end.

Gareth appreciated the resource usage data for diagnosing performance-related bugs, and suggested that the monitoring could be more fine-grained to help identify specific

resource bottlenecks. He reiterated the usefulness of the current setup but noted access restrictions again as a barrier.

Summary:

System performance is generally satisfactory, with meaningful improvements in resource and exception tracking. However, critical data gaps remain—especially around AI workflows and webhooks—while finer monitoring detail and better access control are still needed.

5.4 Monitoring Capabilities

Alex found the collected data useful but mentioned that it requires time and expertise to filter effectively. He suggested improving the interface and filtering tools to speed up data retrieval.

Marc pointed out that while the data is relevant, it is distributed across multiple platforms. He recommended consolidating data to improve usability and reduce the time spent on cross-referencing.

Gareth emphasized the importance of making the data more fine-grained. He said this would allow him to pinpoint issues more precisely, particularly when working with performance or environment-specific bugs.

Summary:

The monitoring data is considered valuable by all participants, but accessing and interpreting it efficiently remains a challenge. Centralization and more detailed, fine-grained metrics are needed to maximize diagnostic potential.

5.5 Integration and Compatibility

Alex reported that the data querying process lacks integration with other tools he uses, requiring manual effort to collect and analyze logs across systems.

Marc had no current integrations either but proposed that mapping network data to resource data in a unified dashboard could enhance utility. He sees potential in integrating monitoring data into development tools for better efficiency.

Gareth stated that none of the monitoring tools are integrated with his main support tools. He still needs to access multiple platforms to gather all the information required for diagnostics.

Summary:

The lack of integration between monitoring tools and user workflows leads to inefficiencies across all roles. There is a clear demand for consolidated dashboards and tighter tool integrations to streamline diagnostics.

5.6 Overall Satisfaction

Alex appreciated the improvements, especially in frontend and backend context data, but reiterated the need for better access to AI-related diagnostics.

Marc expressed overall satisfaction with the system's direction, while noting gaps in monitoring coverage and tool integration as ongoing areas for development.

Gareth felt the system met his basic needs but urged for broader access to backend monitoring to enhance his role's effectiveness.

Summary:

Sentiment is broadly positive regarding the system's evolution. Key areas for further improvement include expanding AI diagnostic capabilities, increasing backend access, and integrating tools more deeply into user workflows.

5.7 Summary of Feedback

The interviews during Study 3 surfaced several key insights:

- **PostHog vs. DataDog:** While PostHog was introduced due to support issues with DataDog, users still prefer DataDog's UI and familiarity. PostHog's learning curve and lower intuitiveness hinder widespread adoption.
- **Context and Monitoring Improvements Appreciated:** New data—especially around context and resource usage—has improved diagnostic clarity.
- **Sampling Concerns Persist:** The sampling strategy in Azure Application Insights, though cost-saving, results in data gaps that impact debugging.
- **Tool Fragmentation and Access Control:** Data is still dispersed across platforms, and access issues remain a significant hurdle, particularly for support staff.
- **Calls for Better Integration:** All roles emphasized the need for centralized, integrated dashboards and easier querying tools.

These insights will directly inform backlog refinement for subsequent iterations and reinforce the importance of balancing functionality, usability, and access when designing monitoring systems.

6. Data to capture status quo of current process

The following data describes the status quo of the bug reproduction process as of 25th May 2025, which includes:

	30/08/2024	04/04/2025	25/05/2025
Number of bug reports created in last 90 days	150	114	90
Number of bug reports marked as non-reproducible in the last 90 days	28(19%)	14(12%)	10 (11%)
Average closing time for bug reports closed in the last 30 days	60 Days	30 Days	28 Days
Add a avg developer time.			
Average number of data items provided in the bug report created in last 30 days	2.3	5.7	5.8
Number of personnel involved in handling a bug report closed in the last 30 days	Min 2 Max 10 Avg 6.2	Min 2 Max 6 Avg 3.9	Min 2 Max 6 Avg 3.1
Number of interactions per bug report for bug report closed in the last 30 days	Min 1 Max 18 Mid 12.1 Avg 9.7	Min 1 Max 11 Avg 6.1	Min 1 Max 12 Avg 5.8
Number of accesses to application monitoring (Application Insights) in the last 30 days:	3	35	40

Compared to previous data, the Lentune bug reproduction process is improving. Non-reproducible bugs continue to decrease, and resource consumption such as personnel and interactions required is also decreasing. The average information in the bug reports remains unchanged, indicating that our current bug report template effectively impacts the collected data points. Similarly, access to the application monitoring system has not increased significantly, likely due to limited training during this study.

7. Summary

Study 3 focused on closing monitoring data gaps in the client, backend, and infrastructure layers to improve bug reproducibility. PostHog was adopted for frontend action tracking but later paused due to high costs and usability issues. Backend and

infrastructure monitoring were enhanced with centralized dashboards for resource and network data, though Azure's sampling limited completeness.

Feedback from developers and support staff highlighted better diagnostics from added context data, but persistent challenges with tool fragmentation, limited access, and missing AI/webhook logs. Monitoring usage increased slightly, while resolution time and non-reproducible bugs declined.

Overall, Study 3 advanced diagnostic capabilities, but emphasized the need for cost control, better tool integration, and broader monitoring coverage in future iterations and following items to be added to the backlog for future improvement:

- I1.2.4 Lack of webhook input/output logging limits diagnostics for integrations.
- I1.4.3 Azure AI's data sampling results in non-deterministic bug traces.
- I1.4.4 Need for real-time SaaS usage cost alerts to avoid financial surprises.
- I2.4.2 Fragmentation of monitoring tools across platforms slows data access.